

Research

An Assessment of Home Stay Tourism at Kaulepani Village of Lamjung Nepal

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Abstract: Homestay has emerged within sustainable development principles of working to benefit local people and to protect fragile natural environments and traditional cultures. Although Kaulepani homestay tourism has received the best homestay award on the occasion of 35th World Tourism Day by the Government of Nepal in 2014, the depth study on tourist's satisfaction has not been carried out yet. Key informant surveys, visitors' surveys, and household questionnaire surveys were carried out to assess detailed information on homestay at Kaulepani village and visitor's satisfaction. As a result, opportunity to enhance the household economy and the utilization of free time were found to be the most important motivating factors to run the homestay program in the area. The homestay has contributed to raise income, promote greenery in the village, raise awareness among the people on sanitation and biodiversity conservation. There is a significant difference with respect to both homestay household and non-homestay household perspective. Along with this, visitors were found to be extremely satisfied with the services and hospitality provided by the villagers. Scenic beauty and cleanliness of the area are the key factors to attract tourist in this area whereas, tourist dislikes transportation facilities and means of communication in the area. Likewise, it has also helped to foster women empowerment in the village making them self- independent by earning money.

Keywords: Homestay, Households, Hosts, Satisfaction, Tourism, Visitors, Women

Introduction

Tourism, in general, denotes the movement of people from one place to another within own country or second countries for several purposes (Bhatta, 2006). Tourism is recognized as a major user of biological resources and source of employment for many Nepalese supporting secondary industries and contributing significantly to the economy (Shrestha, 2001). The tourism industry has grown gradually and undergone various changes to become one of the largest and fastest-growing economic sectors in the world (UNWTO, 2011). According to World Travel and Tourism Council, tourism has contributed 7.9% in Nepal's GDP in 2018 supporting 1.05 million jobs (The Kathmandu post, 2020). Most of the tourism activities are based on commercial tourism and mass tourism. Eco tourism might be an opportunity for ecological resource integrity, environmental conservation, community development and economic development by maintaining low-impact and non-consumptive use of local resources.

Rural tourism normally takes place in rural areas with involvement of whole community by practicing the traditional way of living and giving exposure to their culture and traditional practices (Jamal, et al., 2011). Sirubari(Syangja District) and Ghalegaon in (Lamjung District) first implemented the concept of community homestay which was strategy of Government of Nepal to develop village tourism (Thapa, 2010). At present, many villages in Kaski and Lamjung district are involved to develop their villages as the tourist destination and some have become popular for their homely environment (Dhakal, 2012). Rural tourism includes activities ranging from hiking, horse riding, adventure, fishing, hunting, sightseeing, observing culture heritage, and temples (Kunwar, 1997). Homestay tourism is a form of rural tourism. Home-stay development is one of the strategies that have tremendous potentials to achieve the conservation and sustainable development goals of ecotourism in rural areas while ensuring greater tourist satisfaction (Lama, 2013).

Though the Kaulepani village practicing homestay tourism has already received the best homestay award from the Government of Nepal but due to lack of access and site advertisement, this place is less famous for tourism. Tourist satisfaction became a significant tool to measure the cultural and tradition sector (Peleggi, 1996). Visitor satisfaction should be known for better planning of the business, such variables should be studied. Information on how the homestay program is contributing to achieve its conservation and local development goals is not studied

yet in Kaulepani Homestay. After this study, locals can appropriately manage the site to give better satisfaction to the tourists, which will increase the number of tourist flow. Ultimately it helps to enhance local economies as well as social expectations.

Materials and methods

Study area

Kaulepani village is located on Lamjung district in Province no. 4 at 1600m above sea level. It is around 170km away from Kathmandu and around 6 km away from headquarter of Lamjung district i.e. Besishahar. This village lies in Besishahar municipality and is a touristic area full of natural beauty, biodiversity and cultural diversity. It has mixed habitations of caste and ethnicity (Table 1). The Marsyangdi dam seems like a beautiful green lake from the village. Visitors can get beautiful view of sunrise as well as enchanting 14 Himalayan peaks like Machhapuchhre, Annapurna and Manaslu. Snowfall view in Manslu during winter season is one of the major attractions of this village. Historical and religious places like Lamjung Durbar, Kaulepanidevi Temple and LamjungKalika temple are also attraction points of the village (Khadka, 2016). Throughout the year, the weather remains pleasant in this area.

Figure: 1. Map of the Kaulepani Village, Basisahar, Lamjung, Nepal

Data collection and analysis

Detailed household questionnaire survey was conducted among 25 households of Kaulepani village in which 14 households were practicing homestay program whereas remaining not. Both close and open ended type of questionnaire was prepared for the household survey. Key informants like Homestay Management Committee (HMC), municipality officials and total 45 visitors visiting the homestay were interviewed. Secondary data were collected from various published articles and online portals.

Collected data from the field was analyzed by using Ms Excel and interpreted (Kafle et al., 2020) both qualitatively and quantitatively and presented well in tabular form. Chi- square test was also used to test hypothesis (Karki et al., 2020). The outcomes of the analysis were presented by using various modes such as tabular form, bar diagrams, charts and graphs.

Results

Respondent's characteristics

Out of 25 respondents, the table 1 provides information about gender ratio, age composition, education status and religion of respondents.

Table 1: Respondent's Characteristics

Characteristics	Percentage
Sex	
Male	64
Female	36
Age group	
(0-20)	12
(26-40)	28
(40-60years)	44
(60 above)	16
Education	
Literacy of homestay respondents	57.14

Literacy of non-homestay respondents	54.54
Religion	
Hinduism	48
Buddhism	48
Christianity	4

Motivation of the homestay

From our study, 42 members from 14 homestay households are involved in the homestay business affairs. Out of the members, 47.62% are male and 52.38% are female. It shows that Kaulepani homestay is basically female-led and female managed. The motivation of visit is different on different places. For example: ecotourism of Chuckhola, Makwanpur, Nepal was increasing due to the establishment of Pangolin Park (Dahal, et al., 2019). Ecotourism in Srirubari Shyanja and Ghale Gauu Lamjung is because of rural home stay (Budathoki, 2013).

Response in percentage regarding motivation of operating homestay is given in table 2.

Table 2: Motivation of operating homestay

Motivation of operating homestay	Response in %
Improvement in family income	50.00
Utilization of free time was key factor	28.57
Conservation of nature	7.14
Conservation of culture	14.28

Reason for not operating homestay

The different reasons of not operating homestay are given in table 3.

Table 3: Reason of not operating homestay

Reasons of not operating homestay	Response in percentage
Insufficient money	36.36

Insufficient facilities	27.27
Lack of manpower	27.27
Busy in house works	9.09

Performance of Kaulepani homestay

It is a community based homestay program where Kaulepani Homestay Management Committee (KHMC) assigns visitors to the local host family on a rotational basis. Committee is responsible to collect income and it charges Rs. 1000 per person for one day package and distribute to all community members. They provide overwhelming hospitality by offering curd, garland and tika and serve different varieties of local food like (*kodokoselroti, faparko roti, mohi, gundruk and dhido* or Nepali *dalbhaat*, local chicken meat, etc). Cultural dances, songs and acts are shown in groups to the guests by them. Village Tourism Promotion Forum Nepal (VITOF Nepal) has declared Kaulepani Homestay as the no.1 destination for tourists in 2014. The year 2015 received around 12,000 guests in Kaulepani homestay which is in increasing rate as compared to previous years. Lamjung Chamber of Commerce and Industries has promoted the One Village One Product (OVOP) program in Kaulepani Village and is in its way of making the provision of one green house in one home for cultivating local vegetables, fruits. The other helping hands of homestay are: Gaunshahar Kaulepani Tourism Development Committee (GKTDC), Lamjung Chamber of Commerce and Industries, Rotaract club, Village Tourism Promotion Forum (VITOF) etc.

(a) **Seasonality and occupancy:** As per 14 households conducting homestay program, maximum of them concluded October as the peak season for inflow of guest followed by November, December and January. Feb/Mar/April/May receives medium number of guests whereas months of rainy season like June and July doesn't receive guests at all as per them.

(b) **Saving income from homestay:** Around 71.42% of the respondents concluded that they save 25-50% of income earned from homestay, around 21.42% concluded they save less than 25% income and around 7.14% concluded they save more than 50% income.

Economic sector

Contribution of homestay in economic sector: All the respondent agreed that homestay have increased the income of local people, 92% of respondent agreed that homestay has created jobs to local people, 40% of respondents agreed that homestay have helped in the improvement of infrastructures and 80% of respondent agreed that homestay have helped in generating fund for investment in other community development activities.

Land prices: Out of the total respondents, 20% respondents have said that homestay program have significantly increased the land price and 80% respondents said that homestay program have not increase the land prices.

Environmental sector

In our study, all respondents have said that homestay have raise awareness of the need of conservation and sanitation program, 92% have said that homestay have increased plantation activities, 40% respondents said that homestay have helped in introduction of alternate source of energy.

Consumption of fuel wood: As per all the 25 respondents 20 of them said that consumption of fuel wood is medium whereas 5 of them said it as low.

Homestay program in biodiversity conservation: Kaulepani Village is rich in flora and fauna. The hiking route has more than 20 varieties of *laligurans*, 38 varieties of medicinal herbs. Leopard cat (*Charibagh*), a protected species which is nationally assessed as a vulnerable special by IUCN red list category, is also found here. Some medicinal plants found in Kaulepani village are Chiraito (*Swertia chirayita*), Paniamala (*Phyllanthus emblica*), Chutro (*Berberis aristata*) and Satuwa (*Paris polyphylla*) etc. (Source: Key informant survey and Field survey, 2019). Before establishment of homestay program the local people used to neglect the medicinal herbs, whereas now they know the importance of such herbs and are more concerned towards the conservation of flora and fauna. Fences and bars have been built in such area. As per municipality officials, about 150-200 m above from village a botanical garden is soon to be constructed for its scientific study. Many people visit homestay for scientific research of flora and fauna, bird watching hence homestay households are very much aware about the biodiversity conservation of the site.

Pollution and its level: All of the respondents concluded that the level of air and water pollution is low. 60 % of the respondents responded that level of land pollution is low and 40 % responded as medium. 40 % said that level of noise pollution is low and 60% said as medium. 36% of respondents said that the level of solid waste is low whereas 64 % reported as medium.

Social Impact

Contribution of homestay in youth empowerment

Statement 1: Contribution of homestay on job oriented training program for youth

Table 4: Contribution of homestay on job oriented training program for youth

House hold categories	Rating in Number			Chi-square value	P-value
	Agree	Neutral	Disagree		
Homestay HH	7	4	3	9.07	0.029 (SD)
Nonhomestay HH	1	1	9		

Significant when $p < 0.05$ and the table also shows $p < 0.05$. Therefore, there is significant difference in above statement.

Community people relation after the homestay program

Statement 2: Relation among homestay household

Table 5: Relation among homestay household

Household Categories	Rating in Number			Chi-square Value	P-value
	Very good	Good	Same		
Homestay HH	8	4	2	8.77	0.013(SD)
Nonhomestay HH	2	1	8		

Significant when $p < 0.05$ and the table also shows $p < 0.05$. Therefore, there is significant difference in above statement.

Visitor's satisfaction from homestay

Visitor's characteristics: Altogether 45 visitors visiting the homestay were surveyed at different times to know about their satisfaction towards homestay services. Among them 21 (46.67%) visitors were female whereas 24 (53.33%) were male. Similarly, 15 (33.33%) were from age group below 25, 23 (51.11%) were of the age group 25-40 whereas 7 (15.55%) of them were of age group 40-60. Out of 45 visitor 34 (75%) were Nepalese followed by 6 (13.33%) visitors of Belgium and 5 (11.11%) visitors of New Zealand which shows kaulepani village is famous for domestic tourists.

Purpose of visit: All the 45 visitors were asked about their purpose of visit the response is given in table 6.

Table 6: Purpose of visit

Purpose of visit	Response in Percentage
Refreshment	37.77
Hiking	15.55
Sightseeing/ Bird watching	17.77
Educational	15.55
Cultural	13.33

Quality of food

Visitor's perception about food quality in homestay is given in table 7.

Table 7: Quality of food

Satisfaction Range	Response in Percentage
Extremely satisfied	71.11
Satisfied	28.88

Dissatisfied

0

Quality of accommodation: Visitors were asked about their perception towards the quality of accommodation provided by the homestay response is given in table 8.

Table 8: Quality of accommodation

Satisfaction Range	Response in Percentage
Very satisfactory	20
Normal	11.11
Satisfactory	66.67
Not satisfactory	2.22

Hospitality and friendliness: Through the perception of visitors, the hospitality of host community to the guest was studied and their response is given in table 9.

Table 9: Hospitality and friendliness

Satisfaction Range	Response in Percentage
Extremely satisfied	64.44
Satisfactory	35.55

Beauty of Kaulepani: Visitor response towards beauty of kaulepani is given in table 10.

Table 10: Beauty of Kaulepani

Satisfaction Range	Response in Percentage
Very Satisfactory	88.88
Satisfactory	11.11

Cleanliness of the site: The cleanliness provided by the host community to the guest was also studied through perception of visitors (table 11).

Table 11: Cleanliness of the site

Satisfaction Range	Response in Percentage
Extremely satisfactory	11.11
Satisfactory	55.55
Normal	33.33

Culture and Cultural shows: Perception of visitors towards the culture and cultural shows presented by the host community is given in table 12.

Table 12: Culture and Cultural shows

Satisfaction Range	Response in Percentage
Extremely satisfied	78
Satisfied	22.22

Transportation facilities: Visitor's perception towards the transportation facilities of the site is given in table 13.

Table 13: Transportation facilities

Satisfaction Range	Response in Percentage
Satisfied	6.67
Dissatisfied	71.11
Extremely dissatisfied	22.22

Means of communication: The perception of visitors towards the communication facilities provided by the host community is shown in table 14.

Table 14: Means of communication

Satisfaction Range	Response in Percentage
Extremely satisfactory	11.11
Satisfactory	66.67
Not satisfactory	22.22

Special role of women in promotion of kaulepani homestay tourism: Women group named ‘Sirkhola aama samuha’ plays a crucial role to promote this homestay. They welcome the guests by putting garlands of flowers in a hospitable way. Total 23 female from 14 households having homestay were interviewed. Among them 20 were the member of Sirkhola mothers group and rest 3 were not. Out of 14 members of management committee 10 of them were female which showed that female were in frontline to conduct homestay program in the village. Out of all 23 female respondent’s activities performed by them is given in table 15.

Table 15: Activities performed by woman

Activities performed by woman	Response in percentage
Agriculture and cooking works	100
Making handicrafts	90

Presenting cultural shows	85
Guiding the tourists	15
Decision making	65

Twenty three female respondents from 14 homestay households were interviewed and as per 43.37% of the respondents 25-50% of total income from homestay is contributed by female whereas 56.52% concluded that more than 50% of total income is contributed by female. Out of 23 female respondents from 14 homestay 91.30% of them said that they were able to become self-dependent due to homestay, whereas 8.69% of them said they are still dependent on male members.

Discussion

As increasing trend of tourism to minimize impact on environment and benefit local community, ecotourism is getting popular in Nepal (Acharya et al., 2020). Local people are benefited from homestay tourism in Kaulepani Village of Lamjung, Nepal. A case study of the Muar Homestay Program in Johor state of Malaysia reported positive trend in the operation of homestay. They suggested that homestay tourism had boosted household income. Before joining the Homestay Program, most operation previously earned a monthly income in the range of \$ 119-239. Then, after participating in the Homestay Program, their income increased ranging from \$ 239-359. The study done in Malaysia revealed that homestay program helps to work in team with unity among community people and helps to maintain social tradition, enhance management capacity and perform work efficiently (Ibrahim & Razzaq, 2011). (GU & Wong, 2006) have studied the homestays in Dachangshan Dao in Liaoning Province of North-East China that lies near the coastal region and found that homestays help in creating sustainable tourism with focus on conservation, local people's participation, and management of wastes and water resources. On the other hand, study done by (Neto, 1990) showed that tourism can cause serious environmental problems like depletion of natural resources and environmental degradation. Also the study reported that the majority of individuals who operate homestays are women (Razzaq et al., 2011), But the study conducted by (Thapaliya et al., 2013) on Homestay of Lwang village of Kaski district, Nepal has reported that all the major households as well as community-related decisions are taken by men even if women are working harder than men.

Study done in Malaysia showed that motivation factors for operating homestay were Personal satisfaction, passion in the business and encouragement from friends (Osman et al., 2009). On the other hand, study in Malaysia revealed that economic depression, unemployment, cost-cutting, disappointment with previous job, unsatisfied with the level of income in the previous job and work pressure were reasons of not operating homestay (Osman et al., 2009). Similar results regarding the motivation of homestay, visitor's satisfaction, visitor's activities during the period of stay have been reported by (Thakur, 2013) in his case study of Sirubari Village, Nepal. (Baniya et al., 2017) have analyzed different pull and push factors for tourist arrival and suggested that in Nepal visit of tourist destination inside mainly impacted by the state of natural beauty, cultural richness, and infrastructural advancement.

Current issues

Covid-19 pandemic is hitting the world since December 2019. It has caused abrupt changes in various socio economic sectors such as agriculture and country economy (Timilsena et al., 2020; Dhama et al., 2020). The tourism industry of the world is severely affected by the Covid-19 causing 5.2 % contraction in global GDP in 2020 (World Bank, 2020). Nepal has also imposed lockdown and suspended the international as well as domestic flights since March 23rd which has restricted the flow of tourist. Tourism activities in the country are held for now causing widespread unemployment, economic loss and threatened livelihood for thousands of people. Visit Nepal 2020 campaign has aimed to draw 2 million international tourists by the end of 2020. However, the number of visitors is going downhill by 2% drop in tourist arrivals in January 2020 compared to 2019 (VNY, 2020). The prevailing condition is likely to impact homestay tourism now and tourism after post pandemic is unprecedented. Whilst lack to proper road access to remote destinations, information about the place and lack of tourist service center are some of the major problem faced by visitors. Similarly, Climate induced disasters like erratic rainfall (Gautam et al., 2020; Bhattarai et al., 2020; Sharma et al., 2020) cause landslides, high runoff and damaged of rural roads which also affect the flow of tourism. Many places in Nepal have high tourism potentiality because of primordial landscapes, spectacular views, mystic culture and authentic rural lifestyle. But these places are less explored and not promoted.

Conclusion

From our study, it is clear that people have been benefited from homestay tourism and are able to enhance their standard of living. Opportunity to enhance the household economy and the utilization of free time was found to be the most important motivating factors to run the homestay program. All the respondents said that homestay have raised income and awareness for conservation and sanitation programs. Homestay has also helped in conservation of biodiversity. There is significant difference with respect to both homestay household and non-homestay household perspective. Majority of visitors were very much satisfied with the quality of food, accommodation, hospitality, culture, local environment the beauty of the place, whereas majority of visitors were least satisfied with the transportation and means of communication. Most of the women are the member of homestay management committee and women's group (aamasamuha) and perform activities like cooking special meals, performing cultural shows and making handicrafts for welcoming guests. Majority of woman said that they have become self-dependent due to homestay program.

References

1. Acharya, P., Chetri, H. B., Karki, S., Sharma, P., Tripathi, S., Gahatraj, S., &Gautam, D. (2020). Ecotourism and its impact on local community in Sauraha, Chitwan National Park, Nepal. DOI: [10.36347/sjahss.2020.v08i07.003](https://doi.org/10.36347/sjahss.2020.v08i07.003)
2. Baniya, R., Ghimire, S., &Phuyal, S. (2017). Push and pull factors and their effects on international tourists' revisit intention to Nepal. *The Gaze: Journal of Tourism and Hospitality*, 8, 20-39.
3. Bhatta, D.P. (2006). *Ecotourism in Nepal*. Ghatekulo, Kathmandu.
4. Bhattarai, B., Sigdel, R., Gautam, D., Jandug, C. M. B., & Sharma, J. People's Perception on Climate Change, its Impact and Adaptive Strategies in Kaligandaki Rural Municipality, Syangja, Nepal. DOI: [10.36346/sarjbab.2020.v02i01.001](https://doi.org/10.36346/sarjbab.2020.v02i01.001)
5. Bhudathoki, B. (2013). *Impact of homestay tourism on livelihood: a case study of Ghale Guan, Lamjung, Nepal*. Master's thesis. Norwegian University of Life Science.

6. Dahal, D., Gautam, D., Bhattarai, S., Khanal, L., Baral, K., & Acharya, K. R. (2019). Potentiality of Pangolin based Ecotourism in Chuchhekhola Community Forest, Makawanpur, Nepal. DOI: [10.1729/Journal.22838](https://doi.org/10.1729/Journal.22838)
7. Dhakal, R.N. (2012, June 10). Homestay attracting tourist with local flavor. *The Himalayan Times*. Retrieved from: <http://www.thehimalayantime.com>
8. Dhami, B., Bista, S., Sadadev, B. M., Chhetri, H. B., Poudel, A., Lamichhane, A., ... & Gautam, D. (2020). Overview of Novel Corona virus (COVID-19) and its linkage to economy of Nepal. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.3836903](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3836903)
9. Gautam, D., Bhattarai, S., Sigdel, R., Jandug, C. M. B., Mujahid, A., & GC, D. B. (2019). Climatic Variability and Wetland Resources in Rupa Lake Catchment, Nepal. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.3568477](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3568477)
10. Gu, M., & Wong, P. P. (2006). Development of coastal tourism and homestays on Dachangshan Dao, Liaoning Province, north east China. In Retrieved from International Research Foundation for Development World Forum on Small Island Developing States Publications website www.irfd.org/events/wfsids/virtual/papers/sids_mingpohpoh.pdf.
11. Ibrahim, Y., & Razzaq, A. A. (2011). Homestay program and rural community. Homestay program and rural community, 50-62.
12. Jamal, S. A., Othman, N. A., & Muhammad, N. M. N. (2011). Tourist perceived value in a community-based homestay visit: An investigation into the functional and experiential aspect of value. *Journal of Vacation Marketing*, 17(1), 5-15.
13. Kafle, K., Thanet, D. R., Poudel, P., Gautam, D., Thapa, G., & Bhatt, P. (2020). Status and conservation threats to large mammals of the Laljhadi Mohana Biological Corridor, Nepal. *Journal of Animal Diversity*, 2(2), 16-33. DOI: [10.29252/JAD.2020.2.2.3](https://doi.org/10.29252/JAD.2020.2.2.3)
14. Karki, S., Baral, K., Gautam, D., Jandug, C. M. B., Khanal, L., & GC, D. B. (2019). Assessing the Opportunities of Promoting Ecotourism in Gabhar Valley: A case study from Buffer Zone of Banke National Park. *Asian Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Studies*, 57-66.
15. Khadka, S. (2016). Short cycle- Walk to Kaulepani.
16. Kunwar, R. R. (1997). *Tourism and Development: science and industry interface*. Kathmandu.

17. Lama, Minki (2013): Community homestay programmes as a form of sustainable tourism development in nepal. Available on: <https://www.theseus.fi/handle/10024/68913>.
18. Ministry of Culture, Tourism and Civil Aviation, MoCTCA (2013).Nepal Tourism Statistics 2012. Kathmandu: Government of Nepal
19. Neto, F. (1990). Sustainable Tourism, Environmental Protection and Natural Resource Management: Paradise on Earth?. Growth, 1999, 2000.
20. Osman, I., Ahmad, Z. A., Ahmad, N. H., Husin, A., Bakar, S. A., &Tanwir, N. D. (2009). Following the trail of women homestay entrepreneurs in Malaysia: Understanding their motivation and empowerment. TEAM Journal of Hospitality & Tourism, 6(1), 24-35.
21. Peleggi, M. (1996).National heritage and global tourism in Thailand. Annals of tourism research, 23(2), 432-448.
22. Prasain S. (2019). Nepal tourism generated Rs240b and supported 1m jobs last year: Report. <http://kathmandupost.ekantipur.com.np/news/2019-05-26/nepal-tourism-generated-rs240band-supported-1m-jobs-last-year-report.html> (accessed on 6th August).
23. Razzaq, A. R. A., Hadi, M. Y., Mustafa, M. Z., Hamzah, A., Khalifah, Z., &Mohamad, N. H. (2011).Local community participation in homestay program development in Malaysia. Journal of Modern Accounting and Auditing, 7(12), 1418.
24. Sharma, G., Gautam,D., Jandug, M.C., Bhattarai, S., Baral, K., Manandhar, B., &Sigdel, R. (2019). Climate Change Impacts and Local Adaptation Strategies at Chitlang, Makwanpur, Nepal. DOI: [10.36346/sarjhss.2019.v01i04.013](https://doi.org/10.36346/sarjhss.2019.v01i04.013)
25. Shrestha, U. S. (2001). Bio-diversity Conservation and Eco-tourism: A Case Study from Lang National Park. Himalayan Review, 32, 41-54.
26. Thakur, M. R. K. (2013). Community based village tourism in Nepal: A case study of Sirubari village, Nepal (Doctoral dissertation, Doctoral dissertation, The Global Open University).
27. Thapa, K. (2010). Village Tourism Development & Management in Nepal: A Case Study of Sirubari Village. Retrieved on Jan, 16, 2020.
28. Thapaliya, M., Rai, G. S., Shrestha, A., Parajuli, B., &Pande, O. (2013). Home-stay: Assessment in LwangGhalel. Nepal Tourism and Development Review, 2(1), 105-140.
29. Timilsina, B., Adhikari, N., Kafle, S., Paudel, S., Poudel, S., &Gautam, D. (2020).Addressing Impact of COVID-19 Post Pandemic on Farming and Agricultural

Deeds. Asian Journal of Advanced Research and Reports, 28-35.
DOI: [10.9734/AJARR/2020/v11i430272](https://doi.org/10.9734/AJARR/2020/v11i430272)

30. UNWTO, (2011). Tourism and Poverty Alleviation, Madrid: The United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) 1339.
31. VNY,(2020). Visit Nepal 2020 Tourist Arrivals: 2% Drop in January <https://www.nepalisansar.com/tourism/visit-nepal-2020-tourist-arrivals-statistics/> (accessed on 6th August)

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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